

$\sqrt{10\pi}$ on Khufu's King's Chamber Walls

19 Pieces of π .

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Abstract

In *The King's Chamber Game* [1], I showed how π , φ^2 , e , and others are encoded on the walls of the King's Chamber in the Great Pyramid. The depth and brilliance in the design goes even deeper, as the square root of 10π is also separately encoded, by reading each row as a unit fraction.

Keywords: Egyptology, Giza, The Great Pyramid, Khufu, History of Mathematics, π .

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1 Introduction

In *The Writing is on the Wall: The King's Chamber Game* [1], I showed how the values for π (as 3.142), φ^2 (as 2.618), and e (as 2.718), are built into the block patterns on the walls and floor of the King's chamber in the Great Pyramid. These are illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: King's Chamber plan with π , ϕ^2 , and e .

There are numerous other patterns discussed in that paper. As another example, to illustrate how the designers met multiple conditions at the same time, see Figure 2, which has π at 3.14159.

Figure 2: King's Chamber plan with $\sqrt{2}$, e , $\frac{\pi}{2}$, and π

Flipping the last digits of π is a necessary compromise to allow all the other patterns to work.

For further examples, see [1] and *The King's Chamber Game Diagrams* [2].

In this paper, I show how the blocks also give a reasonable approximation for $\sqrt{10\pi}$ (with π at their usual 3.1416), which is 5.60499777, or 5.605 to 3 digits. The approximation comes out at 5.60515873, also 5.605 to 3 digits. Due to the method used, it is at once both remarkable, and also very difficult to get a more precise value, especially when you consider all the other simultaneous patterns satisfied as shown in *The King's Chamber Game*.

2 $\sqrt{10\pi}$

The method is very simple. We treat the number of blocks in each row on each wall, as the denominator in a unit fraction. For example, the top row of the south wall has 3 blocks. So that becomes $\frac{1}{3}$. Then we simply add all the fractions together.

There is only one special case. The north wall has the large block over the entrance, spanning two rows. This does not meet our requirement of “the number of blocks in each row”. Instead, this block is a “group” indicator, and we exclude it. At the same time, we treat the two rows of five single-height blocks as if they were all in one row (hence my reference to a “group indicator”).

This is illustrated in Figure 3.

West Wall	North Wall	East Wall	South Wall
$\frac{1}{1}$	$\frac{1}{2}$	$\frac{1}{1}$	$\frac{1}{3}$
$\frac{1}{4}$	$\frac{1}{7}$	$\frac{1}{5}$	$\frac{1}{8}$
$\frac{1}{4}$	$\frac{1}{10}$	$\frac{1}{4}$	$\frac{1}{6}$
$\frac{1}{5}$	$\frac{1}{7}$	$\frac{1}{3}$	$\frac{1}{9}$
$\frac{1}{5}$	$\frac{1}{7}$	$\frac{1}{5}$	$\frac{1}{10}$

Figure 3: Converting rows to fractions.

Table 1 shows the summation with a running total.

Wall, row	Block count	Fraction	Cumulative total
West 1	1	1	1.00
West 2	4	$\frac{1}{4}$	1.25
West 3	4	$\frac{1}{4}$	1.50
West 4	5	$\frac{1}{5}$	1.70
West 5	5	$\frac{1}{5}$	1.90
North 1	2	$\frac{1}{2}$	2.40
North 2	7	$\frac{1}{7}$	2.542857143
North 3, 4	10	$\frac{1}{10}$	2.642857143
North 5	7	$\frac{1}{7}$	2.785714286
East 1	1	1	3.785814286
East 2	5	$\frac{1}{5}$	3.985714286
East 3	4	$\frac{1}{4}$	4.235714286
East 4	3	$\frac{1}{3}$	4.569047619
East 5	5	$\frac{1}{5}$	4.769047619
South 1	3	$\frac{1}{3}$	5.102380952
South 2	8	$\frac{1}{8}$	5.227380952
South 3	6	$\frac{1}{6}$	5.394047619
South 4	9	$\frac{1}{9}$	5.50515873
South 5	10	$\frac{1}{10}$	5.60515873

Table 1: The walls, blocks, and fractions

3 Conclusion

Once again the geniuses who designed Giza show the depth of their talent and virtuosity. It is quite remarkable how many ways they found to hide π , while simultaneously doing a multitude of other mathematical tricks.

This provides another hint that the designers were well acquainted with π , challenging the accepted timeline.

Bibliography

- [1] I. Douglas, 'The Writing is on the Wall: The King's Chamber Game', Zenodo, 2022-05-22. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6570342> (visited on 2022-07-19).
- [2] —, 'The King's Chamber Game Diagrams', 2022-05-28. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6598826. [Online]. Available: <https://zenodo.org/record/6598826> (visited on 2023-01-16).